

LBT Switching Procedures for New Radio-based Access to Unlicensed Spectrum

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Abstract—Two channel access procedures are being considered for New Radio-based access to unlicensed spectrum (NR-U) in millimeter-wave (mmWave) bands: omnidirectional Listen-Before-Talk (omniLBT) and directional LBT (dirLBT), which differ on the type of physical carrier sense. Under beam-based transmissions, omniLBT is overprotective and reduces spatial reuse due to exposed node situations, while dirLBT enables spatial reuse, but may create hidden node problems. To address the omniLBT-dirLBT trade-off, this paper proposes LBT switching procedures to dynamically adapt the type of physical carrier sense for LBT in NR-U devices. Switching from dirLBT to omniLBT can be implemented by exploiting already available control messages in NR. Differently, to switch from omniLBT to dirLBT, no information in NR specifications is still available at the time of writing. We define new procedures to measure the overprotection level of spatial reuse provided by omniLBT, and send the switching indication accordingly. Results demonstrate the effectiveness of LBT switching, which enables an independent and dynamic adaptation according to the density and activity of neighboring nodes.

Index Terms—NR-U, mmWave, 60 GHz, beam-based transmissions, dirLBT, omniLBT, LBT switching.

I. INTRODUCTION

The third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) is devoting significant efforts to define New Radio (NR), the Radio Access Technology (RAT) for 5G cellular networks [1], [2]. One of the options that is considered is to allow NR to operate in unlicensed bands, similarly to what was previously proposed in case of Long Term Evolution (LTE) Licensed-Assisted Access (LAA) for the 5 GHz band [3], [4]. NR-based access to unlicensed spectrum (NR-U) is being studied in a NR Rel-15 study item [5] that addresses different bands: the 5 GHz and 60 GHz unlicensed bands, and the 3.5 GHz, 6 GHz, and 37 GHz bands, which are devoted for shared access in the US. In particular, the 60 GHz band is an attractive candidate for NR-U, since it is not very crowded and can offer a large amount of contiguous bandwidth. Currently, only WiGig (Wireless Gigabit, IEEE 802.11ad/ay) devices operate in the 60 GHz band [6].

Despite the large amount of spectrum bandwidth available in the 60 GHz band, the major difference of NR-U/WiGig coexistence therein, with respect to LTE/Wi-Fi coexistence in the 5 GHz band, relies on the mmWave bands propagation characteristics. They require the use of beamforming to overcome propagation limits like the severe pathloss, blocking, and oxygen absorption

[7], [8]. WiGig has already been designed to deal with them by making directionality mandatory at either the access points (APs) or stations (STAs) [6]. Also, in NR, wide support for beam management procedures has been included for base stations (gNBs) and users (UEs) [9]. These beam-based transmissions envisioned in NR and WiGig potentially can cause less interference and enable spatial reuse, but they also change the interference layout, and so does the coexistence framework.

In addition, access to the unlicensed spectrum is subject to regulatory requirements. In case of the 60 GHz band, Listen-Before-Talk (LBT) has been defined as a mandatory procedure in Europe and Japan [10], and so it will be considered in the design of NR-U to meet the regulation worldwide. LBT is a mechanism by which a device should apply a CCA (Clear Channel Assessment) check before using the channel. LBT works across different RATs, and it is adopted by LAA releases, Wi-Fi, and WiGig to accomplish with the regulation. However, it suffers from the hidden node and exposed node problems, because coverages of different devices in a network are different. The problem becomes more complicated when the coverage of sensing and the coverage of transmitting are different. This may occur when an omnidirectional antenna pattern is used for carrier sense (omniLBT) while a directional antenna pattern is used for transmission, leading to a higher chance of a node being exposed, as it happens in WiGig. If the direction of the communication is known, directional carrier sense (dirLBT) may help to improve spatial reuse, but it may also lead to hidden node problems.

To address the omniLBT-dirLBT trade-off, in [11] we proposed a paired LBT solution, in which the physical (PHY) carrier sense at the transmitter is done directionally in paired directions (e.g., the receiver direction and opposite directions) to detect hidden node problems. In [12], we presented a Listen-Before-Receive (LBR) solution, wherein carrier sense at the receiver is triggered and used to complement LBT at the transmitter side. This is also known as receiver-assisted LBT in the NR-U standardization context [13, Sect. 7.6.4]. Still, we could also think of simpler and suboptimal solutions that do not require multiple PHY carrier sensing stages (as in paired LBT) or message exchanges (as in LBR and receiver-assisted LBT) before every channel access, which may introduce a high signaling overhead.

In this regard, our previous results in [12], [11] demonstrate the omnibLBT-dirLBT trade-off. In particular, we show that for low network densities, dirLBT already performs significantly better than omnibLBT, while for high network density, omnibLBT is a good technique. Also, for narrow beamwidths, dirLBT is enough, while for wide beamwidths, omnibLBT is sufficient. This suggests that the type of PHY carrier sense should be properly selected based on the beamwidth configuration and density of neighboring nodes, to address the incorrect behavior of traditional LBT in NR-U with beam-based transmissions. Moreover, dynamic LBT switching methods could also be of interest, to dynamically adapt the channel access procedure to the specific environment encountered by every device, which is the main objective of this paper.

In this paper, we define dynamic LBT switching procedures for NR beam-based access to unlicensed mmWave bands. We detail procedures to switch from dirLBT to omnibLBT, based on the HARQ-ACK (Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request-Acknowledgment) feedback, to detect an excess of hidden node situations. To switch from omnibLBT to dirLBT, new procedures to measure the overprotective level of spatial reuse provided by omnibLBT are proposed, which could be implemented through message exchange among the NR-U devices (gNB and UE) to support the detection of an excess of exposed node situations whenever they arise.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Sections II and III describe the system model and the omnibLBT-dirLBT trade-off, respectively. In Section IV, we present the LBT switching procedures. The simulation results are included in Section V, and Section VI concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider that K_{nr} multi-antenna 5G NR gNBs and K_{wigig} multi-antenna WiGig APs coexist in the 60 GHz unlicensed mmWave band and that all of them use directional transmissions to overcome propagation limits. Each gNB intends to communicate to a NR UE and each AP does so towards a WiGig STA. So, there is a total of $K=K_{\text{nr}}+K_{\text{wigig}}$ pairs (gNB-UE and AP-STA pairs) that attempt accessing to the unlicensed band. We consider a dense indoor network deployment, according to the *indoor mmWave* network topology defined in the NR-U study item [14].

Without loss of generality, we focus on the downlink (DL) access, as similar interference scenarios can be thought of also for uplink (UL) transmission or mixed DL-UL scenarios. Therefore, gNBs/APs are data transmitters, UEs/STAs are data receivers, and all gNBs/APs will do LBT before channel access. Through the paper, we will use index k to denote the k th pair ($k=1, \dots, K$) that can be either a gNB-UE pair or a AP-STA pair, as well as to refer to the devices that compose the pair (i.e., the k th gNB/AP and the k th UE/STA).

For the analysis, we assume that beam-steering has been performed during a well-established beam-training phase, so that every gNB/AP has a transmit beam aligned towards its corresponding UE/STA. On the other hand, omnidirectional reception is assumed at UEs/STAs. A widely-used and simple model to characterize the transmit beams under directional antennas is the cone plus circle model in a two-dimensional scenario [8], [15]. Based on that, the directional antenna pattern of every k th gNB/AP for data transmission consists of a mainlobe with beamwidth θ^k and gain G_{m}^k and a sidelobe of beamwidth $(2\pi-\theta^k)$ and gain G_{s}^k .

The path loss $L_{k,j}$ between two devices that are spaced $d_{k,j}$ meters is modeled by:

$$L_{k,j} = \frac{\beta}{(d_{k,j})^\alpha}, \quad \beta = \left(\frac{c}{4\pi f_c}\right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where α is the pathloss exponent, $f_c=60$ GHz is the carrier frequency, and c is the speed of light. Considering the propagation pathloss, the average received signal power at the k th UE/STA from the j th gNB/AP at a distance $d_{k,j}$ is:

$$P_{\text{rx}}^{k,j} = \frac{\beta}{(d_{k,j})^\alpha} G^{j,k} P_{\text{tx}}^j, \quad (2)$$

where $G^{j,k}$ denotes the transmit antenna gain at the j th gNB/AP in the direction of the k th UE/STA, and P_{tx}^j refers to the transmit power at the j th gNB/AP. Note that $G^{j,k}$ will correspond either to G_{m}^j or G_{s}^j depending on the orientation and shape of the j th gNB/AP transmit beam with respect to the location of the k th UE/STA.

Therefore, the achievable data rate for the k th pair link (gNB-UE or AP-STA) is given by:

$$R_k = W \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_{\text{rx}}^{k,k}}{N_o W + \sum_{j \neq k} P_{\text{rx}}^{k,j}} \right) \text{ [bits/s]}, \quad (3)$$

where W is the channel bandwidth (in Hz) and N_o denotes the noise power spectral density. Those gNBs/APs that do not access the channel, will have a transmit power of $P_{\text{tx}}^j=0$ (and so $P_{\text{rx}}^{k,j}=0, \forall k$).

We consider that LBT is applied at gNBs/APs and focus on its PHY carrier sense, assuming that backoff procedures are also adopted, as specified by the regulation [10]. According to WiGig specifications [6], we assume that omnibLBT is always used at APs. Then, we derive and evaluate different types of PHY carrier senses that can be adopted for LBT at NR gNBs, since they have not been defined by NR-U specifications yet and are under study [13].

III. LBT TRADE-OFFS

Two LBT solutions are envisioned for NR-U to ensure a fair multi-RAT coexistence in unlicensed bands with beam-based transmissions: omnidirectional LBT (**omnibLBT**) and directional LBT (**dirLBT**) [16]. OmnibLBT senses omnidirectionally, while dirLBT senses in a directional manner with the transmit beamwidth, θ^k ,

Fig. 1: Behavior of (a) omniLBT and (b) dirLBT, assuming beam-based transmissions and that LBT is implemented at gNB during an on-going AP-STA transmission, for non-aligned (top) and aligned (bottom) transmissions.

pointing towards the direction of the intended UE. Note that WiGig uses omniLBT, but it also includes support for multiple Network Allocation Vector (NAV) timers (one per STA or beam), i.e., the contention window status are maintained per beam although they are tied to an omnidirectional carrier sense [17].

Under directional transmissions, omniLBT causes overprotection because a transmission is prevented even if a signal is detected from a direction that may not create harmful interference for the intended receiver (i.e., an exposed node problem). This is shown in Fig. 1.(a)-top, for gNB-UE, which could have reused the spectrum but have been prevented by omniLBT at gNB. OmniLBT is only correct when transmissions are aligned in space, see Fig. 1.(a)-bottom. In contrast, dirLBT does not create overprotection because it only senses the spatial direction in which the transmission will be carried out (see Fig. 1.(b)-top). However, in dirLBT, on-going nearby transmissions might not be detected, and hidden node problems may cause interference, as shown in Fig. 1.(b)-bottom. In this case the transmission of the AP lies within the antenna boresight of the UE. The above results in an omniLBT that is overprotective and prevents spatial reuse, and a dirLBT that enables spatial reuse with some hidden node problems. The omniLBT-dirLBT trade-off is shown in Fig. 1 for non-aligned (top) and aligned (bottom) transmissions.

Existing works related to LBT scheme configuration focus on determining/switching the LBT mode, as far as the backoff and contention window size (CWS) update is concerned. In [18], they determine which LBT category is better for uplink transmissions, among the following LBT categories: LBT Cat 2 (no backoff), LBT Cat 3 (random backoff and fixed CWS), or LBT Cat 4 (random backoff and variable CWS, i.e., the approach adopted in LAA releases). Other works adjust the CWS and/or the random backoff number of the LBT procedure [19], configure the LBT pattern regarding the scheduling time intervals [20], or focus on controlling whether LBT is to be performed by a transmitting node before data transmission or not [21]. However, no previous work has addressed the switching of the PHY carrier sense type for LBT, which is the main goal in this paper.

IV. LBT SWITCHING

In this section, we propose LBT switching procedures to address the omniLBT-dirLBT trade-off, and which can be easily incorporated in NR for operation in unlicensed spectrum.

A. omniLBT-to-dirLBT Switching

Switching from omniLBT to dirLBT is required when omniLBT prevents accessing to the channel due to an exposed node problem rather than due to potential interference situation. That is, when gNB-UE are in the situation shown in Fig. 1.(a)-top. In this case, omniLBT is being overprotective and switching to dirLBT could enhance the system efficiency (see Fig. 1.(b)-top). To measure the conservative level of omniLBT, we need to introduce new information and message exchange procedures, since this information cannot be acquired with the current control signaling available in NR specifications. The LBT switching could be based on a new message exchange between gNB and UE, as proposed in the following.

We propose that, when in omniLBT mode, the gNB tracks the number of channel accesses in which the channel was determined as 'busy' by omniLBT, and saves the specific time instant in which that happened. Then, when successfully accessing the channel, the gNB can send information to the UE, through a control channel, about the number of prevented channel accesses and their time instants. We further propose that the UE performs continuous energy detection while in RRC (Radio Resource Control) connected mode, and saves the results in a memory. The UE, after receiving from the gNB information on the missed channel access opportunities and their specific instants, can compare and evaluate if they were effectively due to another nearby transmitting gNBs/APs or not. If they were due to presence of nearby gNBs/APs, omniLBT at gNB was correct, and so the gNB can follow operating with it. If instead there were no other transmitting gNBs/APs, omniLBT was being overprotective, and so switching to dirLBT should be recommended to the gNB.

To indicate the switching, different information elements can be defined. The UE can respond to the received sensing information from the gNB (that indicates the time indexes of gNB channel access attempts in which channel was found busy), through:

- the time indexes in which there was effectively a sensed interferer (channel was busy at UE side),
- the percentage of attempts that the channel was found occupied at UE side, or
- a switching indicator.

When the gNB averages among the feedback of multiple UEs to determine whether to implement the LBT switching or not, reporting a switching indicator from UE side has a lower overhead but provides less detailed information than the other two options.

Fig. 2: Different information exchange procedures to measure omniLBT overprotection and implement LBT switching (omniLBT to dirLBT).

Fig. 3: Different information exchange procedures to measure collisions caused by incorrect dirLBT and implement LBT switching (dirLBT to omniLBT).

Thanks to the message exchange, the gNB knows if it sensed something that the UE did not. In this case, the gNB can switch the LBT strategy to dirLBT. If they both sensed the same, or similar, it is correct to stay with omniLBT strategy.

This information, and how it enables switching to dirLBT, is illustrated in Fig. 2. In the figure, x, y, z denote the time instants in which channel was found busy at gNB side. Assume that only at time instant y the UE found the channel busy (i.e., the received energy was over a threshold). Then, the UE may respond: (a) which of the attempted channel instants were effectively busy at UE side (i.e., y), (b) the percentage of the time instants that channel was busy at UE side (i.e., 33%), or (c) a switching indicator if the percentage of busy instants at UE side is below a predefined threshold (e.g., below a 40%).

B. dirLBT-to-omniLBT Switching

Switching from dirLBT to omniLBT is needed when dirLBT senses the channel as idle but hidden node problems arise. That is, when gNB-UE are in the situation of Fig. 1.(b)-bottom. In this case, dirLBT is incorrect and so a more protective PHY carrier sense approach (omniLBT) could be useful (see Fig. 1.(a)-bottom).

In these situations, the LBT switching can be locally implemented at the gNB based on feedback received from the UE, which is already defined in NR specifications. For example, the gNB could use the number of HARQ-ACK feedbacks received that are NACKs (negative acknowledgment). If the number of NACKs received at the gNB exceeds a given threshold, then switch to omniLBT should be implemented. Otherwise, the gNB would follow with dirLBT, because no excess of hidden node problems was detected.

This procedure resembles the approach adopted in LAA to update the CWS. However, let us note that it has some drawbacks. First, HARQ does not necessarily reflect collisions, e.g., NACK may also occur due to a sudden signal blocking. Second, it is affected by the scheduler policies so that collisions from different UEs may affect differently to the switching actions of LBT, since they will depend on how many and which UEs are simultaneously allocated. Third, since HARQ in NR is based on soft combining techniques (i.e., Incremental Redundancy and Chase Combining), an unsuccessful transmission, due to a collision, may not result in a NACK.

Accordingly, alternative procedures could consider new information from the UEs, not included in NR specifications. For example, we could append one bit to the HARQ-ACK feedback to indicate whether a NACK is caused effectively due to a collision (interferer) or not. This information, and how it enables the switching to omniLBT, is shown in Fig. 3. After the gNB accesses the channel with dirLBT, it can use (a) HARQ-ACK feedback from UE (if NACK), or (b) new collision indicator (sent in case that the received energy at UE is over a given threshold), to implement LBT switching.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

To illustrate the benefits of the LBT switching procedures, we consider a dense indoor network deployment, composed of K pairs that are randomly deployed in a 25×25 m² area. We consider that half of the pairs are NR pairs (gNB-UE), and the other half are WiGig pairs (AP-STA). More precisely, $K_{\text{wigg}} = \lfloor K/2 \rfloor$ and $K_{\text{nr}} = K - K_{\text{wigg}}$. Performance of the DL transmission is evaluated assuming that gNBs/APs operate at carrier frequency $f_c = 60$ GHz with $W = 1$ GHz channel bandwidth and an available power of $P_{\text{tx}} = 10$ dBm. The pathloss model in (1) with $\alpha = 2$ is adopted, which resembles IEEE 802.11ad pathloss model [6]. The noise power spectral density is $N_o = -174$ dBm/Hz. Directional transmission is assumed at gNBs/APs, and omnidirectional reception is used at UEs/STAs. The transmit beam gain at gNBs/APs is fixed to $G_m^k = 10$ dB with a transmit mainlobe beamwidth of $\theta^k = 30^\circ$, $\forall k$, and ideal antenna radiation efficiency is assumed (i.e., $G_s^k = 0$, $\forall k$). The total number of pairs ($K = K_{\text{nr}} + K_{\text{wigg}}$), considering 5 to 60 pairs deployed in the area, is varied through simulations.

According to WiGig specifications, we assume that APs use omniLBT. On the other hand, we evaluate different channel access procedures for NR gNBs (as indicated in the legends of the figures):

- **omniLBT:** gNBs adopt omniLBT, like the WiGig APs.
- **dirLBT:** gNBs use dirLBT.
- **LBTswitch:** gNBs use the proposed LBT switching procedure. We consider that gNBs start with omniLBT and, then, they switch to dirLBT in case that the associated UE sends a switching indicator, and the switching will be applied to the next channel access attempt.

In addition, we also evaluate a **no-LBT** option, wherein all gNBs/APs transmit and interfere to each other. The no-LBT option is not compliant with the regulatory requirements in the 60 GHz band, e.g., for Europe and Japan. However, it is included as a baseline bound to compare to.

The energy detection (ED) threshold for LBT, normalized by the maximum receive antenna gain¹, is set to -74 dBm². We do not emulate backoff processes, and simply consider how many pairs can reuse the spectrum according to the different channel access procedures. Simulation results are averaged among 1000 random deployments, and for each one the gNBs/APs attempt to access the channel in 5 different time instants with random start time.

As performance metrics we use the sum-rate and the mean-rate during channel access. The sum-rate is the sum of data rates: $\sum_{\forall k} R_k$, being R_k defined in (3), and it measures how many pairs can simultaneously access the channel, jointly with their data attained rate. On the other hand, the mean-rate during channel access corresponds to the average of those R_k such that $R_k > 0$, and it is useful to measure the quality-of-service (QoS) obtained by the pairs that get access to the channel. In addition, to account for fairness, we also evaluate the average number of NR and WiGig pairs, separately, that get access to the shared channel according to the adopted NR-U channel access procedure.

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show the sum-rate and the mean-rate during channel access, respectively, versus K . It is observed that, for low K , omniLBT achieves the lowest sum-rate but the highest mean-rate due to its overprotective behavior that prevents access to a large number of pairs, thus reducing the spatial reuse, but improving the obtained QoS. At low K , no-LBT and dirLBT allow for a larger number of simultaneous accesses, and thus an improved sum-rate, but their mean-rate is penalized. As K increases, the sum-rate of no-LBT decreases due to an excess of interference, and also the sum-rate of dirLBT gets saturated by this effect. In that regime, omniLBT improves the sum-rate of no-LBT, and also achieves the largest mean-rate. Interestingly, the proposed LBTswitch can nearly achieve the mean-rate of omniLBT with a sum-rate that is comparable to that of dirLBT for all K , and which is even larger for high network densities (at high K). So, it can get the good parts of every LBT sensing strategy (omniLBT and dirLBT), by properly adapting the type of carrier sense at every gNB in the network as a function of the observed neighboring gNBs/APs density and activity.

¹Note that directional transmissions are considered, but the sensing stage can be performed either directionally or omnidirectionally. Thus, a normalized ED threshold of -74 dBm, by taking into account the receive gain used for sensing, corresponds to -74 dBm for omniLBT and to -64 dBm for dirLBT.

²The noise power, for $W=1$ GHz and $N_o=-174$ dBm/Hz, results in -84 dBm, and thus we consider -74 dBm as the ED in omniLBT to account for the noise figure.

Fig. 4: Sum-rate (in Gbits/s) vs. the total number of pairs (K).

Fig. 5: Mean-rate (in Gbits/s) vs. the total number of pairs (K).

Next, we evaluate the system fairness and the QoS obtained by NR and WiGig pairs, separately, for $K=40$ (i.e., $K_{nr}=20$ and $K_{wigig}=20$). Fig. 6 depicts the average number of NR pairs and WiGig pairs that access the channel, separately, for the different channel access procedures adopted by the gNBs (omniLBT, dirLBT, LBTswitch). Fig. 7 shows the mean rate during channel access for NR pairs and WiGig pairs, separately³. It can be observed that dirLBT allows for a larger number of simultaneous NR accesses to the channel due to its non-overprotective behavior, as compared to omniLBT. This also reduces the number of WiGig accesses, since they find the channel occupied, when more gNBs get access through dirLBT, as well as the average rate of all nodes. On the other hand, LBTswitch is able to enhance the fairness of NR pairs as compared to omniLBT, since more NR pairs get access to the channel, while not affecting negatively the number of WiGig accesses and their average rate. In this sense, we can also claim that LBTswitch better performs in terms of coexistence with other technologies, than dirLBT.

³Note that we have accounted for the achievable rate, which should be constrained by the specific RAT operational principles in practice.

Fig. 6: Number of NR and WiGig pairs that get access to the channel for different strategies adopted by gNBs. $K=40$ (20 NR and 20 WiGig pairs).

Fig. 7: Mean-rate during channel access (in Gbps/s) of NR and WiGig pairs, separately, for different strategies adopted by gNBs. $K=40$ (20 NR and 20 WiGig pairs).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes LBT switching procedures for NR beam-based access to unlicensed mmWave bands, in which the type of physical carrier sense at the transmitting nodes (gNBs) is dynamically adjusted between dirLBT and omniLBT according to the environment observations. Procedures to implement the LBT switching, as well as the new required information and mechanism to measure the overprotective level of omniLBT, are defined. Simulation results show that LBT switching achieves a mean-rate close to that of omniLBT with a sum-rate that is comparable to that of dirLBT. In addition, it offers a fairer access to the channel, among both NR and WiGig nodes. This demonstrates that a dynamic LBT switching is able to adjust correctly the type of carrier sense at every gNB, thus avoiding hidden node problems, which appear under dirLBT, and stimulating spatial reuse, which is prevented by omniLBT, dynamically. Future work involves the evaluation of LBT switching procedures in a system-level coexistence simulator that includes the PHY carrier sense as well as the backoff processes at MAC layer for NR and WiGig.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partially funded by Spanish MINECO grant TEC2017-88373-R (5G-REFINE) and Generalitat de Catalunya grant 2017 SGR 1195. Also, it was supported by InterDigital Communications, Inc. The authors would like to thank Alpaslan Demir, Mihaela Beluri, and Sanjay Goyal for the fruitful discussions.

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